

Artificial Noise Management for Securing Backscatter Communication Networks: Current Advances, Open Challenges, and Future Directions

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Abstract—Backscatter Communication Networks (BCNets) hold significant promise for advancing the ubiquitous Internet of Things (IoT) due to their capabilities in energy harvesting and ultra-low-power consumption. However, their broadcast and open nature expose them to serious security risks and privacy breaches that hinder their widespread applications. Artificial Noise Management (ANM) has recently emerged as a solution to these vulnerabilities. By deploying artificial noise to disrupt potential attackers while mitigating its negative impact on legitimate receivers through advanced signal processing techniques, ANM creates a significant disparity in decoding capability between the attackers and the legitimate receivers. This disparity makes attackers unable to accurately recover the complete content of the communication, thus preventing information leakage. Despite substantial recent research on ANM within BCNets, a comprehensive review is notably absent from the literature. To fill this gap, this paper presents a systematic survey on ANM in BCNets. We begin by proposing a set of evaluation criteria that a sound ANM scheme should satisfy. Then, we introduce a taxonomy of ANM techniques in BCNets and conduct a thorough review of the current state-of-the-art by employing these criteria to analyze their pros and cons. Finally, we outline open challenges and suggest future research directions based on our serious review.

Index Terms—Backscatter communication networks, artificial noise management, security, Internet of Things.

I. INTRODUCTION

Backscatter Communication (BC) has emerged as a key enabling technology for the Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystem due to its superior energy efficiency and sustainable operation [1]. Unlike traditional active wireless transmission, BC allows batteryless or energy-constrained Backscatter Devices (BDs) to communicate by harvesting ambient Radio Frequency (RF) energy and reflecting incident signals to convey information. These unique advantages make BC particularly suitable for deployment in challenging environments and diverse practical IoT scenarios, such as remote healthcare monitoring [2], object tracking [3], and ubiquitous device identification [1], where long-term energy sustainability and ease of deployment are essential user requirements.

Despite these promising attributes, the inherently open and broadcast nature of wireless channels in Backscatter Com-

munication Networks (BCNets) exposes them to significant security vulnerabilities. Users of BCNets typically require secure, reliable, energy-efficient, and computationally simple solutions, given the resource constraints and diverse operational environments of BDs. Unfortunately, cryptographic methods cannot fully satisfy these stringent demands due to their high computational complexity and excessive energy consumption. Consequently, there is an urgent need for specialized, lightweight security approaches that explicitly consider the practical limitations and unique characteristics of BCNets, enabling robust and secure communications suitable for large-scale IoT deployments.

To address the unique challenges in resource-constrained BCNets, Physical Layer Security (PLS) has emerged as a promising approach due to its low computational complexity and modest hardware requirements. Traditional PLS techniques, such as Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum (DSSS) and Frequency Hopping Spread Spectrum (FHSS), enhance security by dispersing signal energy over a broader frequency band. This dispersion increases resistance to eavesdropping and provides robustness against narrowband interference. However, these methods involve complex synchronization, bandwidth inefficiency, and vulnerabilities to sophisticated attacks with advanced signal processing ability, thus facing difficulty in developing resource-constrained BCNets. In contrast, Artificial Noise Management (ANM) has recently garnered attention as an alternative PLS approach in BCNets. ANM operates on two primary fronts. First, it transmits unpredictable Artificial Noise (AN) to jam attackers, which inherently provides resistance to sophisticated passive attacks aimed at extracting confidential data and sensitive privacy. Second, to counteract the potential degradation of legitimate communication caused by the broadcast nature of AN, ANM incorporates advanced signal-processing techniques (e.g. Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO), beamforming) to mitigate such interference and maintain the Quality of Service (QoS) for legitimate devices. Together, these strategies establish a decoding gap between attackers and intended recipients, effectively preventing attackers from recovering the complete communication content and achieving secrecy capacity from an information-theoretic perspective [4]. Therefore, by leveraging inherent wireless phenomena such as signal and channel fading, ANM provides a low-complexity, adaptable solution that is particularly well-suited for deployment in resource-constrained BCNets.

However, a comprehensive survey of ANM techniques in BCNets is still missing. Such a survey would establish a

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TABLE I
COMPARISON OF OUR SURVEY WITH OTHER EXISTING SURVEYS
✓: satisfy; ×: not satisfy; ✓-: satisfy, but not comprehensive.

Work	BCNets	Classification	ANM Concept Summary	Qualitative Evaluation
[5]	×	✓	×	×
[6]	✓-	×	×	×
[7]	✓	×	×	×
Ours	✓	✓	✓	✓

taxonomy of existing ANM techniques, summarize key ANM concepts, and provide a qualitative evaluation of the state-of-the-art, thus exploring open challenges and clarifying future research directions. *Hamamreh et al.* [5] classified and reviewed Physical Layer Security (PLS) techniques proposed in the literature, including several applications of using AN to achieve PLS. Highly related, Lu et al. [6] provided a review on AN-based protection for wirelessly powered networks, which includes BCNets scenarios. However, their survey lacks a comprehensive classification on ANM techniques. Among 13 reviewed schemes analyzed in their review, only two of them are about ANM in BCNets. In addition, a recent study [7] reviewed emerging AI and machine learning approaches for ambient backscatter systems, addressing topics such as interference management and resource allocation. However, while this work provides valuable insights into AI-driven enhancements, it does not offer a comprehensive taxonomy or a qualitative evaluation specifically focused on ANM techniques in BCNets. Furthermore, the surveys mentioned above do not systematically summarize the concept of ANM in the current state of the art. To highlight the uniqueness and differences of our survey, we compare our work with related studies in Table II.

In this paper, we conduct a comprehensive survey on ANM in BCNets. We begin by introducing the fundamental knowledge of BCNets and ANM, along with a detailed illustration of ANM's role in BCNet (Section II). Subsequently, a set of evaluation criteria is proposed to establish the benchmarks that an ANM scheme should satisfy in terms of security, effectiveness, and generality (Section III). Following this, we outline a taxonomy of current ANM schemes in BCNets and examine their strengths and weaknesses by employing the proposed criteria (Section IV). Finally, drawing insights from the review results, we figure out unresolved issues, discuss their associated challenges, and provide directions for future research endeavors (Section V).

II. BACKGROUND

In this section, we introduce the fundamentals of BCNets and ANM, followed by an overview of how ANM is applied to BCNets.

A. BCNets

BCNet is a communication network in which devices exchange information by reflecting incident RF signals from external carrier sources rather than generating their own. As illustrated in Fig. 1, BCNet can be modeled based on involved entities and their communication behaviors. In the Monostatic Backscatter Communication (MoBC) model, a full-duplex Access Point (AP) both transmits RF signals to a BD and

Fig. 1. Overview of using ANM in different BCNet models.

receives its backscattered signals for bidirectional communication. The co-location of the RF source and receiver in MoBC facilitates effective link control, though the round-trip path loss inherent to the process results in weak signal strength and heightened self- and environmental interference that restricts MoBC primarily to short-range applications such as Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) systems [1]. In contrast, the Bistatic Backscatter Communication (BiBC) model employs a dedicated Carrier Emitter (CE) to transmit RF signals that power the BD, with an independent receiver capturing the backscattered signal. This separation mitigates the round-trip path loss, thus supporting broader communication ranges despite potential interference from the CE. Additionally, Ambient Backscatter Communication (AmBC), a derivative of BiBC, utilizes ambient RF sources, such as TV towers and Wi-Fi routers, as the CE to enable energy-efficient communication in various applications, including wearables and transportation [2].

B. ANM

1) *ANM Introduction*: ANM is a systematic mechanism that aims to enhance the security of a communication network by exploiting AN to create a decoding disparity in decoding capability between the attackers and the legitimate receivers. A sound ANM mechanism should contain three fundamental components: *AN deployment*, *AN cancellation*, and *performance optimization*. The *AN deployment* process involves designing and transmitting AN signals over wireless channels, including selecting signal type, structure, and data, as well as transmission techniques like encoding, modulation, and multiplexing. In BCNets, noise generation methods are broadly divided into two categories: **random noise generation**, which uses stochastic processes to produce unpredictable signals that effectively disrupt eavesdroppers, and **structured noise generation**, which employs predefined patterns or seeded distributions to enable precise AN cancellation at legitimate receivers. *AN cancellation* aims to mitigate the negative impact of AN on legitimate communications. It achieves this by coordinating between the AN transmitter and legitimate receivers, ensuring that the transmitted data remains unaffected by AN. Lastly, *performance optimization* focuses on improving communication quality within ANM through strategy resource allocations, such as time-frequency resource sharing, modulation optimization, power allocation, etc. According to the different requirements of the application scenarios, the design of suitable optimization strategies can enhance security or maintain QoS under security constraints.

TABLE II
COMPARISON AMONG ANM, DSSS AND FHSS

Technology	Principle	Attack Resistance	Applications	Complexity	Spectrum Efficiency
DSSS	Spreads signal via pseudo-random codes	JA, NEA	GPS, CDMA	high	low
FHSS	Frequency hopping to reduce interference	JA, NEA	Bluetooth, Military	high	low
ANM	Artificial noise to jam eavesdroppers	PA	IoT, 5G/6G	low	high

JA: Jamming Attacks, NEA: Narrow-band Eavesdropping Attacks, PA: Passive Attacks

2) *ANM in BCNets*: Deploying ANM in BCNets offers significant potential by offloading complex computations from resource-constrained BDs to more capable entities such as APs and CEs. Fig. 1 provides an overview of ANM implementation in BCNets. The ANM deployment is chosen specifically because resource-constrained BDs cannot support high computational complexity methods typically required by traditional security approaches. Hence, offloading complexity to more powerful entities is a practical necessity in real-world IoT deployments. In the MoBC scenario, random noise generation is adopted primarily because of its implementation simplicity, low computational overhead, and effectiveness in confusing potential attackers. Given the computational capability of the APs, they can dynamically adjust critical parameters, such as AN power and time offset, based on real-time channel state information, ensuring both effective interference against eavesdroppers and high-quality legitimate signal decoding. Meanwhile, in the BiBC, structured AN generation becomes necessary due to the physical separation of APs and CEs. Random AN would complicate precise interference cancellation at legitimate receivers due to synchronization difficulties. To address this, structured AN based on a pre-negotiated seed is chosen, as it allows precise cancellation of the AN signals at legitimate receivers. This method enhances system security by effectively preventing unauthorized decoding attempts without significantly compromising the reliability of communication between legitimate entities. Such explicit choices in AN generation and cancellation methods are directly aligned with practical user requirements of high security, low computational burden, and robust QoS preservation in realistic backscatter communication scenarios.

3) *Comparison of ANM with DSSS/FHSS techniques*: Table II summarizes and compares the key characteristics of ANM with traditional spread spectrum techniques, DSSS, and FHSS. DSSS employs pseudo-random code spreading to protect against jamming attacks, which is common in Global Positioning System (GPS) and Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) systems. However, it suffers from bandwidth inefficiency and complex synchronization due to high spreading factors. FHSS, which uses continuous frequency hopping to counter both jamming and eavesdropping, is favored in applications like Bluetooth and military communications but is limited by lower spectral efficiency. In contrast, ANM strategically injects unpredictable AN to directly degrade the signal quality for potential eavesdroppers, inherently countering sophisticated passive attacks such as eavesdropping and traffic analysis. Moreover, by operating within the existing frequency band, ANM achieves high spectral efficiency. In addition, ANM enhances PLS without the need for precise synchronization or complex spectrum management techniques. These

advantages render ANM particularly suitable for resource-constrained and dynamic IoT environments as well as modern 5G/6G applications.

III. EVALUATION CRITERIA

In this section, we propose a set of criteria to evaluate the performance of ANM schemes in BCNets from the following perspectives, i.e., security, effectiveness, and generality.

A. Criteria on Security

An ANM scheme should ensure security by satisfying the following criteria.

1) *Passive Attack Resistance (PAR)*: PAR refers to the ability to prevent passive attackers from successfully obtaining valuable information. Passive attackers aim to extract communication data or sensitive traffic information by intercepting and analyzing signals emitted from legitimate devices, e.g., through eavesdropping and traffic analysis. In addition, passive attacks are regarded as the prior step of many serious threats since attackers can tamper or falsify communication data based on wiretapped results. Therefore, supporting PAR stands as a foundational objective of ANM schemes in BCNets.

2) *Conditionally Active Attack Resistance (CAAR)*: CAAR represents whether a scheme can prevent conditionally active attackers from gathering sufficient preparatory data. Conditionally active attacks in BCNets rely on intercepted information to launch subsequent active assaults. For example, attackers attempting to spoof legitimate BDs must first acquire valid identity information. An ANM scheme that can support CAAR shows its strong ability to prevent information leakage.

3) *Active Attack Resistance (AAR)*: AAR represents whether a scheme can prevent active attackers from damaging BCNets. Active attackers in BCNets can manipulate the signals to influence the signal transmission procedure or manipulate devices or systems' environments, such as fake AP attacks and jamming attacks, which could lead to serious data leakage and communication interruption. An ANM scheme should incorporate measures to mitigate such attacks, highlighting its superiority in security.

4) *Attack Traceability (AT)*: AT refers to the ability to trace an attacker's location. The location information of an attacker allows the AN transmitter to emit AN toward the attacker's position, maximizing the interference for the attacker. Therefore, AT emerges as a security enhancement mechanism in ANM that should be considered.

B. Criteria on Effectiveness

Effectiveness is used to evaluate whether the ANM can be used for practical usage and makes use of resources adequately. The attributes related to effectiveness include but are not limited to the following metrics.

Fig. 2. Taxonomy and development of ANM schemes in BCNets.

1) *Resource Allocation Optimality (RAO)*: RAO refers to the ability to improve ANM performance in BCNets through effective resource allocation. For example, the allocation between the power of AN and data signals directly reflects the trade-off between the jamming performance for attackers and the communication rate performance between legitimate devices. Supporting RAO shows the effectiveness of an ANM scheme in using resources adequately.

2) *Optimization Algorithm Computational Complexity (OACC)*: OACC measures the speed at which a performance optimization algorithm performs for a given data or sample input size in ANM. ANM scheme with high OACC leads to a long processing time, which hinders its implementation in resource-constrained BCNets. Therefore, OACC should be considered when assessing the accessibility and suitability of an ANM scheme in BCNets.

3) *Deployability (De)*: De represents whether a scheme is validated through real-world implementation. In reality, the performance of an ANM scheme in BCNets can be susceptible to complex channel conditions resulting from environmental changes in motion, reflection, and fading. This can cause the scheme to not perform as expected. Therefore, an ANM scheme should consider satisfying De to demonstrate its potential in practical deployment.

4) *Self Interference Avoidance (SIA)*: IA represents whether an ANM scheme can avoid the negative effects of its transmitted AN on legitimate devices. The inherent broadcasting nature of AN mixes it with transmitted data, potentially degrading the QoS performance during communications. This is the main interference existing in ANM schemes. Hence, an ANM scheme should support SIA, which preserves the integrity of legitimate communications.¹

C. Criteria on Generality

Generality measures the applicability of an ANM scheme for various scenarios, including the following metrics.

1) *Mobility (Mo)*: Mo refers to the capability to preserve regular communication quality in a scenario with mobile devices. In many BCNet applications, such as wearables, UAV, and IoV networks, the device is mobile, causing changes in amplitude, phase, frequency, and spatial characteristics with

various speed levels. This could degrade the communication quality of BCNets. For example, a fixed AN or message signal transmitting power may not work for devices that gradually move away because their received power is degraded by a longer distance. Therefore, an ANM scheme that can support mobility is easy to apply in many practical scenarios.

2) *Channel State Information Independence (CSII)*: CSII represents whether an ANM scheme can operate effectively without CSI knowledge. CSI knowledge is highly expected in ANM, which helps adjust resource allocation to achieve desired performance. However, in practice, CSI is often inaccessible, or its estimation may incur errors. Thus, a robust ANM scheme should be suitable for unknown or imperfect CSI conditions. Depending on channel type, CSII can be divided into two categories: Eavesdropping Channel State Information Independence (ECSII) and Legitimate Channel State Information Independence (LCSII).

3) *Multiple Device Support (MDS)*: MDS represents whether an ANM scheme can effectively work in multi-device scenarios and adapt to the change for the scale of a BCNet. The constant deployment of BCNet led to a growth in the number of devices involved, which caused inter-interference and resource competition in practice. Thus, supporting MDS demonstrates the potential of the ANM scheme for widespread deployment. In this article, we consider the MDS of BCNets in a comprehensive way regarding both Multiple BD Support (MBS) and Multiple AP Support (MAS).

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW AND ANALYSIS

This section reviews the current literature of ANM in BCNets. We begin by proposing a taxonomy of ANM schemes in BCNets and elaborating on their progression. Subsequently, we evaluate their strengths and weaknesses based on the predetermined criteria and conclude with a discussion of the research status and shared characteristics within each category. The findings are presented in Table II.

A. Taxonomy of ANM in BC

In Fig. 2, we classify ANM schemes in BCNets and illustrate their development. Initially, we classify the existing ANM schemes into two primary categories based on the application objective of AN: ANM for PLS and ANM for covert communications.

¹The SIC evaluated herein is not interpreted as traditional full-duplex self-interference cancellation; rather, it represents the negative effect of AN introduced by a legitimate administrator on any legitimate devices.

1) *ANM for Physical Layer Security*: The scheme in this category aims to emit AN towards the position of attackers to hinder attackers from intercepting signals and decoding the desired signals, reducing their received Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). Within this category, we further classify existing schemes into two groups: *research on security* and *research on QoS under security constraints*. The former focuses on the theoretical performance analysis and optimization of security aspects. For example, optimizing the Secrecy Rate (SR) performance where the data can be securely transmitted without being decoded by eavesdroppers [1], [3], [8]. Other security performances, such as Interrupted Possibility (IP) [9] and Outage Probability (OP) [2], are also investigated. The latter classification focuses on maintaining efficient and reliable data transmission, i.e., QoS metrics, under security constraints. Works such as [10] and [11] have explored throughput and energy harvesting efficiency under SR constraints, respectively.

2) *ANM for Covert Communications*: Applying ANM in achieving covert communications differs from PLA approaches, as it does not require emitting AN towards attackers' locations. Instead, it employs AN to obfuscate legitimate transmission activities. For example, a transmitter can mix AN with data signals to obfuscate them, thwarting attackers from distinguishing between the two. This strategy protects both the transmitted data and the communication activities. Similarly, we further subdivide this category into *research on security* and *research on QoS under security constraints*. The former encompasses studies like [12] and [13], which analyze and optimize covertness in the MoBC and AmBC models, respectively. In contrast, the latter category features research such as the work in [14], [15], which investigates QoS performance, including energy efficiency and throughput BCNets under covertness constraints.

B. ANM for Physical Layer Security

1) *Research on Security*: To save energy in AN generation, Yang *et al.* [1] proposed using Randomized Continuous Waves (RCW) in RFID systems, simultaneously serving as both AN and charging signals. The RCW, characterized by a random distribution, allows legitimate readers to decode backscattered signals via correlation for SIA support, whereas attackers lacking the distribution knowledge cannot effectively filter this multiplicative noise. This inherently supports SIA and removes the need for additional power for AN generation. Furthermore, RAO and ECSII are achieved by dynamically adjusting RCW power to optimize its SR using only the statistical information of the eavesdropper's channel, thereby eliminating the need for instantaneous CSI. PAR is only partially addressed, as PLS alone does not prevent attackers from inferring transmission behaviors. Other aspects, such as CAAR, AAR, AT, De, Mo, and MDS, are not considered.

To counter active attacks, Zhao *et al.* [8] proposed a channel estimation protocol combined with an adaptive ANM strategy. Specifically, the CE protocol employs both least squares and linear minimum mean square error methods to accurately estimate CSI of legitimate and eavesdropper channels, fully supporting CSII. Utilizing the estimated CSI, the authors developed a hierarchical security game model to dynamically optimize AN and CW power allocation to maximize the

secrecy rate, thus achieving AAR. Moreover, by optimizing the power allocation between data and AN, their approach achieves RAO with linear complexity. However, their research does not consider aspects like SIA, MDS, Mo, De, CAAR, and AT.

To enhance the generality of ANM in BCNets, Li *et al.* [9] designed a Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA)-based ANM mechanism in an AmBC system. This design accounts for real-world factors, including imperfect interference cancellation deployment and errors in channel estimation, which satisfy SIA and CSII. Specifically, the authors employed successive interference cancellation to distinguish the signals from multiple devices and AN, optimizing the trade-off between reliability and secrecy performance under realistic hardware impairments. Moreover, closed-form analytical expressions for OP and IP were derived, explicitly analyzing their asymptotic behaviors in high SNR regimes, thus clearly illustrating the reliability-security trade-off. However, their study does not consider aspects such as RAO, De, AAR, CAAR, AT, and Mo.

Aiming to employ ANM in practice, Li *et al.* [2] introduced a novel ambient ANM framework deployed within a Vehicles-to-Pedestrians (V2P) network. Specifically, they assume that wearable BDs are attached to pedestrians and exploit surrounding ambient signals to communicate with the receiver in a car. To eliminate the ambient signals at a receiver, they posit that the ambient source emits seed-based AN and pre-negotiates a seed with the receiver to avoid the interference caused by the AN, thus supporting SIA. Meanwhile, it is difficult for attackers to filter the ambient signals without the knowledge of the seed. In this way, they achieve PLS between the BD and the receiver. Furthermore, they derived the metrics of the OP and IP probability, but the resource allocation problem was not investigated, which cannot support RAO. In addition, they cannot support CSII since they assume that the CSI is known. The criteria of De, AAR, CAAR, AT, Mo, and MDS are not considered.

Bai *et al.* [3] exploited MIMO techniques and ABF to transmit RCW directionally, achieving PLA for large-scale BDs in UAV-enabled networks. By leveraging analog beamforming with a uniform planar array and multi-carrier RCW signals, they optimized UAV positioning, beamforming vector, and power allocation jointly through a block coordinate descent and successive convex approximation algorithm. Their RCW design achieves effective SIA, similar to the approach in [1]. Furthermore, they formulated the secrecy rate maximization problem and derived approximate closed-form expressions to simplify the secrecy rate analysis. However, their non-convex optimization algorithm involves relatively high computational complexity. Moreover, accurate CSI is essential for beamforming optimization, limiting the support for CSII. Other aspects like Mo, De, AAR, and AT are not considered in their work.

Discussion: Efforts in this domain have been significant, with advancement from satisfying basic security criteria to meeting practical needs. Over time, PAR and AAR have gradually been supported, followed by a large number of works that can support RAO by optimizing the security metrics. Notably, some of the schemes have investigated CSII and MDS. Nevertheless, aspects such as CAAR, De, AT, and Mo

TABLE III
SUMMARY AND COMPARISON OF ANM SCHEMES IN BC NETWORKS

Cat.	Ref.	Main Contribution	PAR	CAAR	AAR	AT	RAO	OACC	De	SIA	Mo	CSII		MDS		
												LCSII	ECSIII	MBS	MAS	
①	[1]	Introduce RCW and finite-alphabet input	●	○	○	○	●	$\approx O(N \log M)$	○	●	○	○	○	●	○	○
	[8]	First consider and address active attacks	●	○	●	○	●	$O(N)$	○	○	○	○	●	●	○	○
	[9]	Consider CSI estimation errors and multiple APs	●	○	○	○	○	-	○	●	○	○	●	●	○	●
	[2]	Exploit ambient signals as AN in a V2PNet	●	○	○	○	○	-	○	●	○	○	○	○	○	○
	[3]	Beamforming for multiple BDs in a UAV network	●	○	○	○	○	$> O(MN^8)$	○	●	○	○	○	○	○	○
②	[10]	First investigate Th in a multi-BD BCNet	●	○	○	○	●	$O(MN^{2.5})$	●	○	○	○	○	○	●	○
	[11]	Consider nonlinear energy harvest and investigate EHE	●	○	○	○	●	$> O(MN^2)$	●	○	○	○	○	○	●	○
③	[12]	Achieve CC in BiBC and Optimize CR	●	○	○	○	●	$O(N)$	○	●	○	○	○	○	○	○
	[13]	Joint optimization to achieve covertness	●	○	○	○	●	$O(N^3 M)$	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
④	[14]	Achieve CC in AmBC and Optimize EE	●	○	○	○	●	$O(N)$	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
	[15]	Achieve CC in BiBC and Optimize Th	●	○	○	○	●	$O(M)$	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
Average Achievable Proportion (%)			68.1	0	9.1	0	72.7	-	9.1	45.4	0	18.2	27.3	27.3	9.1	

①: Research on security in physical layer security; ②: Research on QoS in physical layer security; ③: Research on security in covert communications; ④: Research on QoS in covert communications.

PAR: Passive Attack Resistance; CAAR: Conditionally Active Attack Resistance; AAR: Active Attack Resistance; AT: Attack Traceability; RAO: Resource Allocation Optimality; OACC: Optimization Algorithm Computational Complexity; De: Deployability; SIA: Self Interference Avoidance; Mo: Mobility; CSII: Channel State Information Independence; LCSII: Legitimate Channel State Information Independence; ECSIII: Eavesdropping Channel State Information Independence; MDS: Multiple Device Support; MBS: Multiple BD Support; MAS: Multiple AP Support.

V2PNet: Vehicle to Pedestrian Network; Th: Throughput; EHE: Energy Harvesting Efficiency; CC: Covert Communication; EE: Energy Efficiency. M: the number of iterations of the algorithm; N: optimized variables.

The results presented in the table are analyzed in the review or derived from the original results in the corresponding paper.

●: fully supported; ○: not supported; ●: mentioned, but without concrete analysis or simulations for validation/partly supported; -: not mentioned/related.

are generally overlooked.

2) *Research on QoS under Security Constraints*: In practice, effectively mitigating the adverse impact of AN on legitimate devices is challenging, as the broadcasting of the signals makes the AN mix with data signals. This interference could degrade the QoS performance in BCNets, potentially rendering the networks inaccessible, such as communication interruption and energy shortage. Therefore, Wang *et al.* [10] conducted a detailed analysis of throughput performance in a typical multi-BD MoBC system where an AP employs time division multiplexing techniques to transmit AN and charging signals to multiple BDs simultaneously. They derived closed-form expressions for the SR and throughput by incorporating channel fading and interference effects, and then proposed an iterative approximation method based on a block coordinate descent technique to optimally allocate power between the AN and charging signals under a specified SR constraint.

Then, recognizing that a linear energy harvesting model does not accurately capture practical BD behavior, they extended their work in [11] by incorporating a non-linear energy harvesting model. This extension not only adjusts the power allocation strategy but also refines the analysis of energy harvesting efficiency, with detailed convergence proofs and complexity analysis included in their derivations.

Discussion: The two schemes exhibit similar characteristics. They achieve RAO by optimizing the resource allocation

strategy; however, their optimization algorithm incurs polynomial computational complexity, which may limit scalability in large-scale networks. MBS is supported by using time division multiplexing to enable multiple BDs, and De is partially supported since they conduct a proof-of-concept experiment in a simplified single-BD scenario. Moreover, both studies assume perfect CSI for legitimate and eavesdropping channels, thereby not satisfying the CSII criterion. Critical aspects such as CAAR, AAR, AT, SIA, Mo, and MAS are not considered, presenting clear opportunities for future research improvements.

C. ANM for Covert Communications

1) *Research on Security*: Liu *et al.* [12] proposed a covert communication framework tailored for AmBC systems. In the framework, the transmitter emitted ambient RF signals, which were backscattered by the BD for communication purposes. Simultaneously, the receiver deployed AN to disrupt potential eavesdroppers, preventing them from detecting the backscattering signal from the BD. They mathematically derived the closed-form expression for Maximum Detection Error Probability (MDEP) of the attacker's decision on legitimate transmissions, and optimized it by adjusting the power range of the transmitted AN, thereby facilitating support for RAO with linear complexity. Specifically, they employed a rigorous derivation based on the Neyman–Pearson detection framework

to obtain the MDEP expression, carefully accounting for the statistical properties of both the ambient RF signals and the AN interference. Additionally, their optimization algorithm utilizes iterative linear approximations to efficiently balance the trade-off between AN power allocation and covert performance, ensuring that the computational overhead scales linearly with the number of system parameters.

Recently, *Gao et al.* [13] introduced a covert communication framework specifically tailored for a BiBC system, focusing on joint optimization to achieve covertness. They leveraged AN together with precise control over the backscatter coefficients and transmission power at the source. By carefully managing these parameters, the system ensures high MDEP performance and achieves PAO. However, the optimization problem is notably non-convex, which is solved through an alternating optimization algorithm that requires polynomial complexity. In their work, the authors rigorously derived the joint optimization problem by modeling the impact of backscatter coefficient variations and AN power fluctuation on both the MDEP and covert rate. Moreover, they provided a detailed convergence analysis supported by theoretical proofs and simulation results that validate the efficiency and polynomial complexity of the proposed alternating optimization algorithm.

Discussion: Commonly, research in this area can fully satisfy PAR, as the covert nature of communications prevents passive attackers from detecting communication patterns, thus safeguarding both the data and the traffic information. However, they only consider single-BD scenarios, depend on known CSI assumptions, and require successive interference cancellation at the receiver, which indicates that they cannot support MDS, CSII, and SIA, respectively. In addition, they fail to consider conditionally active and active attacks. Other criteria like CAAR, AAT, AT, De, and Mo are generally neglected.

2) *Research on QoS under Security Constraints:* The pursuit of the two schemes mentioned above entails operational costs due to adjustments in AN power consumption. To address this issue, *Wang et al.* [14] proposed an ANM scheme aimed at enabling covert communications within BiBC systems while enhancing energy efficiency. Their scheme involved a dedicated CE transmitting RCW to power the BDs and obfuscate the presence of backscattered signals. The CE could eliminate the RCW by leveraging its prior knowledge, thus supporting SIA. To further mitigate energy costs while preserving covertness, the authors derived closed-form expressions for both energy consumption and detection error metrics, integrating them into a unified optimization framework with linear complexity.

In a BiBC setting, *Gu et al.* [15] introduced a novel covert communication scheme, combining AN injection and reflection coefficient optimization to safeguard the transmission against passive attacks. Specifically, the carrier signal and the AN are transmitted by a CE simultaneously to supply energy for a BD while safeguarding the BiBC system. Unlike general covert communications that primarily consider covert rate, this work innovatively considered MDEP to ensure communication covertness. They introduced a linearly iterative optimization method for power control, artificial noise injection, and reflection coefficient adjustment. This approach significantly boosts

the transmission rate while ensuring a robust MDEP level against eavesdroppers.

Discussion: The ongoing research in this domain remains nascent, with only two existing schemes investigating energy efficiency and the throughput performance of ANM in BC-Nets. These schemes share several common characteristics concerning evaluation criteria. Both are capable of resisting PAR due to the inherent stealthiness of covert communications; however, they do not address criteria such as CAAR, AAR, or AT. They achieve RAO primarily through optimizing resource allocation strategies. Additionally, neither scheme supports CSII, as both rely on prior knowledge of the CSI for both legitimate and eavesdropping channels. Finally, DE, SIA, Mo, and MDS aspects remain unaddressed in their work.

V. OPEN ISSUES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Based on the in-depth review above and the evaluation result of Table II, this section specifies the issues and analyzes the challenges faced by ANM in BCNets, following suggestions to guide future research directions.

A. Conditionally Active Attacks Resistance

Issue: The current literature still lacks an ANM scheme that can fully resist conditionally active attacks. Achieving CAAR demands relatively cumbersome steps in analysis, design, and justification. For instance, ANM schemes require a comprehensive adversary model detailing how attackers operate, as well as a robust security justification that demonstrates how the proposed scheme defends against such attacks. Although prior studies, such as [3], have indicated the potential utility of ANM in mitigating these attacks, detailed modeling and substantiation of these defenses remain insufficient.

Future Direction Suggestion: Future research should prioritize fortifying defenses against conditionally active attacks by integrating meticulous adversary models, customized design strategies, and exhaustive security analyses. Such efforts will help to rigorously substantiate the efficacy of ANM schemes in countering conditionally active threats, ensuring that the proposed methods are both theoretically sound and practically effective.

B. Active Attacks Resistance

Issue: There are relatively few ANM schemes that support the AAR in BCNets. Addressing active attacks poses significant challenges because the limited power of the BD signals can easily be overwhelmed by stronger signals from active attackers. Notably, attackers often transmit signals only during the data transmission phase of the BD to conserve energy, as observed in [8].

Future Direction Suggestion: Future endeavors should focus on designing adaptive ANM mechanisms that exploit the specific transmission patterns of attackers. For example, transmitters could employ covert communication strategies that strategically use AN to mislead attackers into believing that the BD is not actively transmitting data. Additionally, leveraging the BD's energy harvesting capabilities could allow the BD to counteract the attacker's signals effectively, thereby enhancing overall resilience against active attacks.

C. Attacks Traceability

Issue: Current research often overlooks attack traceability, even though it plays a crucial role in enhancing AN interference performance. By enabling the transmission of AN in a specific direction toward an attacker, traceability can significantly bolster the security framework. However, accurately tracking an attacker is challenging due to the substantial resource demands required for signal detection and precise position tracking.

Future Direction Suggestion: Future work should focus on integrating attack traceability into the broader ANM framework—encompassing AN deployment, AN cancellation, and performance optimization—to strengthen overall security in BCNets. In addition, researchers should develop innovative AN configurations that facilitate precise attacker localization, for instance, by analyzing reflected AN signals to accurately discern attackers' positions.

D. Mobility Support

Issue: Mobility is generally underexplored in current ANM research. In BCNets, devices can exhibit a wide range of mobility, from low-speed scenarios involving wearable devices or sensors on pedestrians to high-speed applications such as vehicular networks and UAV communications. These varying mobility levels introduce rapid fluctuations in channel conditions that challenge the static configuration of ANM parameters. In particular, high mobility may render CSI outdated, thereby disrupting the precise alignment required between the transmitted AN and its cancellation at a legitimate receiver.

Future Direction Suggestion: Future work should focus on developing an adaptive ANM framework that dynamically adjusts system parameters in response to real-time channel variations under different mobility levels. For low-speed mobility, adaptive ANM could employ lightweight tracking mechanisms for gradual CSI updates. Given the relatively stable channel characteristics, simple periodic feedback and incremental resource adjustments (such as power allocation and timing offset) can effectively maintain robust performance and precise AN cancellation at legitimate receivers without significant computational overhead. To maintain effective interference cancellation and ensure reliable communication under high-speed mobility, integrating machine learning-based optimization in the ANM could be particularly beneficial. By incorporating predictive algorithms to forecast channel fluctuations, the system can preemptively optimize ANM settings to accommodate high-mobility scenarios, thereby mitigating the adverse effects of rapid channel variations on both security and QoS.

E. Optimization on Computational Complexity and Energy Consumption

Issue: While most contemporary studies prioritize RAO, they often overlook the computational overhead associated with algorithms in multi-resource and multi-device scenarios, leading to high-order polynomial computational complexity. In addition, among the reviewed papers, only [14] explicitly considers the energy consumption issue for resource-constrained

BDs. This neglect of high energy consumption and computational complexity can undermine both the security and QoS performance of ANM in BCNets, particularly in IoT devices where energy efficiency, low computational complexity, and spectrum efficiency are critical.

Future Direction Suggestion: Future research should prioritize the development of lightweight and energy-efficient ANM algorithms. Promising approaches include leveraging machine learning techniques, such as deep learning and reinforcement learning, to pre-train models that can rapidly infer optimal parameters under dynamic network conditions. Additionally, addressing energy consumption requires a comprehensive evaluation that incorporates real-world energy consumption models and detailed computational complexity analyses, thereby guiding the design of ANM schemes that balance robust security performance with minimal resource consumption. Furthermore, future studies could investigate integrating dynamic spectrum allocation and intelligent frequency selection strategies in multicarrier systems, such as cognitive radio techniques and adaptive channel assignment, into ANM algorithms. These methods can enable real-time optimization of spectral resources, mitigating interference and reducing energy consumption by dynamically selecting optimal carriers based on current channel conditions. By leveraging such spectrum management approaches, multicarrier systems can enhance overall security and efficiency in resource-constrained IoT environments.

F. Artificial Noise-aided Interference Suppression

Issue: Current ANM research predominantly focuses on canceling the self-interference of AN on legitimate devices [1], [2] or on optimizing resource allocation to maintain QoS under security constraints [10], [11]. These approaches primarily prevent QoS degradation caused by AN, but they do not explore the potential of using AN to actively enhance the inherent QoS of BCNets. The challenge lies in designing AN deployment strategies that can neutralize environmental interference—such as signals from co-channel external devices, multipath interference, and ambient noise—at the reception end.

Future Direction Suggestion: Future research should investigate the design of AN schemes where the content and transmission characteristics of AN are crafted to be mutually reversible with environmental interference at legitimate receivers. By doing so, AN can not only jam attackers but also suppress external interference, thereby improving the overall QoS in BCNets. Integrating interference suppression into the ANM framework could transform AN from a source of potential degradation into a tool for enhancing network performance.

G. Systematic Deployment

Issue: Current ANM schemes face limitations in fully satisfying De in BCNets due to hardware constraints and high implementation costs. A primary challenge is generating genuinely random AN, which is crucial to prevent attackers from decrypting communications. Numerous studies [1]–[3], [8], [12], [14] assume the inherent randomness of AN, yet producing truly random signals demands sophisticated hardware and intricate signal processing techniques. Moreover, advances

in filtering methods, such as adaptive filtering and Kalman filters, pose a risk that attackers might subvert the randomness of AN.

Future Direction Suggestion: Future research should focus on enhancing the precision of hardware fabrication and developing robust signal processing methods to generate and verify authentic random AN. By addressing these challenges, researchers can better justify the randomness of AN and reduce the risk of subversion, thereby accelerating the prototype implementation of ANM schemes within BCNets. In addition, future work should develop standardized ANM protocols that ensure compatibility with existing and emerging wireless standards and networks, such as cellular or Wi-Fi systems, to leverage their complementary security and communication resources. Such cross-network collaboration could improve overall system robustness by allowing coordinated interference cancellation and shared CSI knowledge on potential attackers, but it also raises challenges in ensuring seamless protocol interoperability and synchronization.

Additionally, further research is needed to explore practical applications of ANM in emerging BCNet scenarios, such as smart cities, healthcare, and IoT environments. A comprehensive protocol suite that integrates ANM with upper-layer services will facilitate robust and seamless deployment in real-world systems.

H. Applications of ANM in Emerging Scenarios

Issue: Existing research on ANM in BCNet has mainly focused on conventional BCNet models, leaving emerging scenarios relatively underexplored, such as Multi-Hop Backscatter Networks (MH-BCNets), smart environments, and healthcare. In these new application scenarios, unique challenges arise due to increased device density, diverse interference patterns, and dynamic operating environments. Addressing these challenges requires adapting and extending ANM techniques beyond traditional deployments. In what follows, we introduce the future potential deployment of ANM in these scenarios.

Future Potential Scenario 1: Multi-hop Backscatter Networks. In MH-BCNets, signals traverse multiple BDs before reaching their destination, leading to cumulative noise, increased path loss, and more complex interference patterns. ANM can be effectively adapted to secure multi-hop routes by leveraging its low complexity and energy efficiency, which are well suited to resource-constrained environments. For example, intermediate nodes could collaboratively backscatter AN to obfuscate genuine information transmissions, facilitating covert communications. Furthermore, deploying auxiliary devices to emit AN for jamming attackers can also introduce security capacity in such a system. A robust AN cancellation mechanism is essential to mitigate self-interference, ensuring that legitimate communications remain unaffected.

Future Potential Scenario 2: Smart Environments. Smart environments, including smart agriculture and smart cities, face challenges such as high device density, dynamic interference, and stringent requirements for energy-efficient, secure communications. Future research should explore the deployment of BCNets in these application domains by conducting detailed case studies. These studies could assess how ANM strategies can be optimized to counteract interference and

enhance security in scenarios ranging from monitoring environmental conditions in rural settings to managing traffic and public safety in urban areas. Insights gained from these case studies will help refine ANM and cancellation techniques to better address the specific interference and mobility challenges present in smart environments.

Future Potential Scenario 3: Healthcare. In healthcare, ongoing mobility and strict data integrity requirements pose risks to sensitive medical data and the overall integrity of healthcare communications. ANM in BCNets offers a promising solution for securing low-energy IoT devices in healthcare communications. Future studies should focus on pilot deployments in clinical environments to validate the effectiveness of structured AN, such as seed-based distributions, in ensuring robust AN cancellation even under high mobility. By integrating practical case studies into research, it is possible to bridge the gap between theory and practice, ultimately enhancing the reliability and security of BCNets in healthcare applications.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a systematic review on ANM in BCNets. We began by introducing the fundamental concepts of BCNets and ANM, and then established a set of evaluation criteria specifically designed to assess the security, effectiveness, and generality of ANM schemes. Then, we classified and reviewed cutting-edge ANM schemes, revealing both their strengths and limitations by employing the proposed criteria. Through our in-depth analysis, we identified several critical issues, including challenges in conditionally active/active attack resistance and reliable attack traceability. We also highlighted the significance of resource allocation, energy saving, and the need for standardized protocols and adaptive strategies to address dynamic real-world conditions. Future research should focus on developing advanced adversary models, energy-efficient algorithms, and adaptive ANM schemes to enhance the security and scalability of BCNets in emerging IoT applications.

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